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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document constitutes a preliminary load analysis report for the MegaRoller wave energy converter (WEC), presenting performance and ultimate load metrics for a range of design situations. It includes the definition of a set of critical design load cases (DLCs), the description of the approach followed to conduct the load analysis effort, and the key results from the priority load calculations.

This deliverable is the main output of Task 1.3 and has the overall objective of contributing to increase the understanding of the wave-structure interaction problem affecting the device, informing the design process conducted in WP2. The priority load characterisation effort was conducted using a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator), introduced in Task 1.2. The WEC-Sim model developed in the context of Task 1.2 was updated to consider the specificities related to the MegaRoller WEC (e.g. WEC geometry, power take-off (PTO) properties). The use of a fully-coupled hydrodynamic model enables a detailed assessment of the influence of the distributed loading contributions over the WEC prime mover, i.e. the flap, accounting for the coupled nature of interaction(s) between the flap and the PTO load sources.

In a preliminary step, the impact of different control strategies on the performance of the WEC was assessed, to select a suitable strategy in terms of power performance and reliability. Two strategies were considered: a passive logic, where the PTO damping coefficients remain unchanged throughout each sea state; and an active, sub-optimal logic, where the PTO damping coefficients are updated on a wave-by-wave basis. Following initial comparisons, the load calculation effort was conducted using the sub-optimal control strategy. Further developments such as the conceptualisation of a structural dynamics module was also implemented in the MegaRoller WEC model, contributing to a more detailed understanding of the wave-structure interaction problem.

Following the presentation of the updated WEC-Sim model, this report provides the rationale for the definition and prioritisation of appropriate DLCs, including the environmental conditions and the design situations associated with each. The shortlisted DLCs focus on design situations that are likely to affect the design of the MegaRoller WEC, and that in turn can be directly associated with the design of the PTO. The DLCs were selected based on the review of a generic failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA) matrix from the SDWED¹ (Structural Design of Wave Energy Converter Devices) project, and through discussions with AWE. Key results from the priority load calculations are presented, aiming to support the structural design of the 1MW MegaRoller WEC, namely the PTO sub-systems (in WP2) and of the test bench (in Task 1.6). The results documented indicate that DLCs 2.1 and 7.1 are likely to be critical to PTO design. Additionally, the results also identify some of the potential limits of the rigid body formulation in face of the estimated load envelope, e.g. when considering loads that may jeopardize the structural integrity of the prime mover. Finally, and although the MegaRoller project focuses on the development of the PTO system, the findings stress the importance of coupled assessments to identify interdependencies that could relate to the prioritisation of the survival of the PTO vs. survival of the WEC.

In order to ensure that the simulation model provides a reliable description of the MegaRoller PTO and of the upgraded test bench behaviour, verification, pre-validation and (where possible) validation of the simulation model will be conducted in the context of Task 1.5. In particular, it is envisaged that the data collected when operating the MegaRoller PTO in the upgraded test bench in Task 5.2 may inform a validation exercise related to the simulation model.

¹ <https://www.civil.aau.dk/Project+websites/sdwed/>

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of the Document

This document constitutes a preliminary load analysis report for the MegaRoller wave energy converter (WEC), presenting performance and ultimate load metrics for a range of design situations.

The document provides a rationale for the definition and prioritisation of the design load cases (DLCs) to consider in the load characterisation exercise. The DLCs shortlisted focus on design situations that are likely to affect the primary design of the MegaRoller WEC, and that in turn can be directly associated with the design of the PTO. The report also details the calculation effort conducted, in particular the environmental conditions, the power take-off (PTO) settings and the type of analysis that apply to each proposed DLC. Finally, key metrics and associated results from the load model are provided, focusing on Ultimate Limit State (ULS) and Fatigue Limit State (FLS) conditions.

This deliverable is the main output of Task 1.3, aiming to increase the understanding of the wave-structure interaction problem to inform the design process conducted in WP2. The load characterisation effort was conducted using a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator), introduced in Task 1.2 [D1.1, 2018]. A nonlinear model of the MegaRoller WEC was developed to assess the influence of the distributed loading contributions over the WEC prime mover, i.e. the flap, accounting for the coupled nature of interaction(s) between the flap and the PTO load sources.

This document is organised in six main sections. Following this introduction (Section 1), a technical description of the MegaRoller WEC is provided in Section 2. The load analysis model is then described in Section 3, focusing on the updated features to replicate the MegaRoller specificities. The rationale for the shortlisting of DLCs is detailed in Section 4, in what constitutes a calculation guide for the load analysis effort. The key results addressing load calculations are then presented in Section 5. Finally, the recommended next steps, in particular regarding the connection to the design process (in WP2 and Task 1.5), are detailed in Section 6.

1.2 Acceptance Criteria

This document adheres to the description of the deliverable provided in the Grant Agreement [GA, 2018]:

- *“List the design load cases and describe the type of load acting on each case. The value of loading for each design load case is given in this report as well”.*

2 TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE MEGAROLLER WEC

A high-level technical description of the MegaRoller WEC is provided in this section, including its key subsystems and modes of operation.

2.1 General Description

A general presentation of the MegaRoller WEC is provided in [GA, 2018]. Essentially, the WEC can be described as an oscillating wave surge converter (OWSC) with a hydraulic PTO, where piston pumps have an interface with the panel via a drive train. The pistons pump hydraulic fluid inside a closed circuit, which is enclosed inside a hermetic structure and not exposed to the marine environment. The high-pressure fluids are fed into hydraulic motors that drive an electricity generator. Finally, the electrical output from the generator is then fed to the electric grid via a subsea cable (see Figure 2.1).

The device operates in nearshore regions at depths of between 8 and 20 meters, approximately 0.3-2km from the shore. It is anchored to the seabed and, depending on tidal conditions, it is mostly or fully submerged during operation. A series of devices can be deployed in an array to create a wave farm. Since the WEC is constructed as a modular individual unit, there is no natural upper limit to the number of devices that can be used in an array, therefore offering a high-level of scalability [GA, 2018].

Figure 2.1 1MW OWSC device (left) and OWSC conversion process (right) [GA, 2018]

2.2 Key Subsystems

The key focus of the MegaRoller project is to develop the PTO of the first MW-level WaveRoller OWSC based on specific hardware and software innovations [GA, 2018]. The upgraded MegaRoller PTO is designed in a modular structure with a cylinder unit on each side of the panel and a standardised power unit, bringing together five key hardware innovations [GA, 2018]:

- A modular design to achieve the most compact power electronics design for both subsea and shore units. The modular structure brings flexibility to the design, allowing a variable number and size of cylinders and accumulator racks, as well as a modular cooling package and generator to adapt to the local resource.
- Twin drive trains with the equivalent to a shaft mounted drive to withstand wave loads, comply with axial loads and maintain a counter momentum to the panel torque load. Twin drive trains require one (or both) of the drive trains to be flexibly mounted.

- Intelligent cylinders to increase the power density by combining oil flow controls in an innovative hydraulic block design that integrates cooling with hydraulic pipes. This enables a reduction of the number of components and the volume required, therefore reducing installation and servicing costs, while increasing the power density.
- A standardised central power unit to bring efficient fluid-to-electricity setup combining electrical and hydraulic components. The central power unit optimises the power production and efficiency in all wave conditions, especially in partial power based on motors and generators always driven with optimal parameters.
- A novel accumulator arrangement to increase power density and enable the optimal usage of accumulators for advanced energy storage control. It is envisaged that some of the accumulators are located within the drive train cylinder unit and others within the standardised central power unit.

The MegaRoller project also aims to develop advanced PTO control, with five software innovations enabling better power plant control and precise power prediction according to utility specifications [GA, 2018]:

- A wave-by-wave prediction model, using an enhanced Echo State Networks (ESNs) adaptive machine learning algorithm, to estimate the next waves based on the time series of past activity.
- A wave-by-wave damping control strategy, where force control parameters are adapted on a wave-by-wave basis to maximize power capture. The project will also seek to reduce global bending loads due to the waves approaching from an oblique heading by controlling the counterforce wave-by-wave.
- An advanced energy storage control strategy, where the storage capacity, smoothing and power output are optimized based on the predicted forthcoming waves and customer preferences.
- An advanced efficiency control strategy, where motors and generators are driven with optimal parameters, based on wave predictions.
- A supervisor controller, to manage the individual (sometimes conflicting) control requests and harmonize performance at array-level. The system will optimize the power output of multiple devices so multiple devices can be connected to a single power cable and so that utilities can have a higher control.

2.3 Modes of Operations

A high-level machine state diagram was provided in [D2.3, 2018], defining at a high-level the transitions between the main modes of operations. Essentially, the main modes of operations can be summarised as follows:

- The standby mode, which corresponds to a state where the hydraulic system is charged, but the cylinders are disengaged.

- The idling mode, which corresponds to a state where the hydraulic system is working, but the unit is not generating any force.
- The running mode, which corresponds to a state where the electric generators produce a counter moment.

Additional information on the different modes of operations can be found in [D2.3, 2018]. In this report, the load analysis exercise conducted focuses essentially on two machine states: one where the PTO is producing power (the running mode) and one where the PTO is not converting any power (e.g. standby or idling mode) – see also Section 4.5.

3 MEGAROLLER WEC-SIM MODEL

The MegaRoller WEC load analysis model is described in this section, focusing on the updated features to replicate its specificities. The WEC geometry and mass properties were provided by AWE², whilst other key features (e.g. PTO and control models) were agreed with AWE following an internal project meeting³.

3.1 Overview

As described in [D1.1, 2018], WEC-Sim simulation models are constructed on a multi-body basis, as a collection of linked components with specific physical properties. In the standard WEC-Sim release, (v3.0), these components include wave-activated rigid bodies and joints at which PTO forces may be applied.

The WEC-Sim model of the MegaRoller is introduced in [D1.1, 2018], and summarised below. This section aims to further describe potential updates identified in [D1.1, 2018] that were implemented in the context of the MegaRoller project.

The primary functions of WEC-Sim that interact to solve the multi-body dynamics of the WEC model include:

- Wave class, that defines the wave conditions for the simulation.
- Body class, that defines the body properties (e.g. mass, moment of inertia, centre of gravity, hydrodynamic properties).
- Constraint class, to connect the WEC bodies to one another and the seabed with defined DOFs constrains.
- PTO class, which connects the WEC bodies to one another (and possibly to the seabed) by constraining DOFs and applying linear damping and stiffness.

The following sections provide a more detailed description of the different features of the WEC-Sim models for the MegaRoller WEC investigated in this report.

3.2 Baseline Structural Model

The WEC structural properties are represented in the standard release of WEC-Sim as rigid bodies with mass, inertia and hydrodynamic properties. The relative position of each body is defined by the location of their centre of gravity in the global reference frame. The component connectivity is defined in the constraint and PTO classes that connect the bodies to the global reference frame. For constraint and PTO classes, the user also needs to specify their location relative to the global reference frame. A Simulink chart representing the multi-body structure implemented in WEC-Sim is illustrated in Figure 3.1.

² M. Vuorinen (2018), [1072] MEGAROLLER WP1 - WEC-Sim model: pre-validation and verification input, [E-mail] message to P. Laporte-Weywada, dated 23/05/2018

³ P. Laporte-Weywada, WP1 discussions – Load characterisation effort and required inputs, [internal memo], dated 31/10/2018.

Figure 3.1 Schematic of the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model in Simulink

At a high-level, each PTO subsystem illustrated in Figure 3.1 includes a translational PTO block, described further in Section 3.4, and two rotational constraints to enable the rotation of the PTO with the pitching motion of the flap. These are further illustrated in Figure 3.2. The hydrodynamic bodies (in orange in Figure 3.2) are inserted for stability purposes, and are attributed dummy mass, volume and inertia properties.

Figure 3.2 Schematic of the MegaRoller PTO constraint blocks in Simulink

The model also includes an end-stop block that aims to restrain the pitching motion of the flap. The end-stop was modelled as a rotational constraint with stiffness properties. The stiffness force starts acting when the pitching angle reaches an angle above +/- 50 degrees.

The bearings are located inside the base body, two meters below the the bottom of the flap. The PTOs are located at the bottom of the flap, at each extremity – see Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 Schematic of the MegaRoller WEC prime mover (flap), exemplifying the locations of the bearings and the PTOs

The geometric and mass properties of the MegaRoller WEC prime mover are summarised in Table 3.1. Finally, the main dimensions of the WEC are illustrated in Figure 3.4.

Table 3.1 Key geometric and mass properties of the MegaRoller WEC prime mover (flap)

Property	Value
Volume (m ³)	750
Mass (kg)	250,000
Distance of centre of gravity from the bottom of the flap (m)	2.3
Moment of inertia I_{yy} (kgm ²)	5,000,000
Location of the bearings from the seabed (m)	1
Location of the PTO from the seabed (m)	3

Figure 3.4 MegaRoller WEC dimensions (in m) – side and top views. The red and green axis correspond to the x and z axis of the coordinate system, respectively (origin at water level)

It should be noted that, in the current rigid body dynamics implementation, the hydrodynamic loading on the WEC does not affect the external surfaces of the structure. However, these hydrodynamic and structural interactions could potentially be of significant relevance for the overall design of the WEC if e.g. hydrodynamic loads excite fundamental frequencies of the structure, leading to potentially destructive resonance effects. In order to assess the impact of the distributed loading contributions over the flap on the PTO system, an advanced structural dynamics module was implemented in WEC-Sim. Such module is further described in Section 3.7.

3.3 Hydrodynamics Model

The hydrodynamic coefficients and the wave exciting force associated with the main floating body were derived in NEMOH and loaded into the WEC-Sim model. The derived hydrodynamic data includes first-order (linear) and weakly nonlinear quantities (instantaneous hydrostatic and Froude-Krylov forces). The model geometry used by the flow solver was defined using Rhino, and the mesh of the mean wetted profile is shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5 Example of the NEMOH mesh defined for the MegaRoller WEC

In order to account for the change in hydrodynamic properties with the pitching motion of the flap, the WEC-Sim model of the MegaRoller WEC was also extended to enable the use of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients. These were derived from multiple boundary element method (BEM) simulations, with the mean position of the flap at a range of pitch angles (referred to as “*BEM angle*”). Simulations for angles ranging between -40 and $+40$ degrees were completed, with a 10-degree spacing.

During the WEC-Sim simulations, and when the database implementation is activated, the model calculates the hydrodynamic forces using the hydrodynamic coefficients derived at the relevant *BEM angle* at the current time step (referred to as “*current angle*”). To avoid instabilities, a hysteresis approach was implemented: at each time step, the code compares the *current angle* to the range of *BEM angles*. A new *BEM angle* is then only selected if the difference between BEM and current angles is larger than 7.5 degrees (i.e. $\frac{3}{4}$ of the BEM angle spacing of 10 degrees). Section 5.2.2 presents the results of a preliminary investigation on the assessment of the influence of the database implementation on the WEC performance.

3.4 Power Take-Off (PTO) and Control Model

The PTO forms part of a WEC’s power conversion chain (PCC), usually being the primary system that converts the wave-induced motion into mechanical or electrical power. For OWSCs such as the MegaRoller WEC, the electricity is converted from the back-and-forth movement of the bottom-mounted flap. In a preliminary step, and to assess the potential benefits on the power performance of a wave-by-wave damping control algorithm, a comparative study looking at the influence of the PTO profile / controller logic in the WEC response was conducted.

A range of idealised profiles based on the prime mover’s pitch radiation damping coefficients were defined. Figure 3.6 shows the radiation damping coefficients in pitch derived from the BEM model in NEMOH plotted against the incoming wave period (left), and the PTO torque profiles against pitch angular velocity for a range of wave periods (right). It is important to note that these profiles correspond to a sub-optimal solution that assumes that only the real part of the mechanical impedance can be controlled.

Figure 3.6 Idealised PTO profiles: a) Normalised radiation damping coefficients in pitch; and b) PTO torque profiles (in MNm) against pitch angular velocity (in rad/s)

Using the PTO torque profiles shown in Figure 3.6, two strategies were considered:

- A passive logic, where the PTO damping coefficients remain unchanged throughout all sea states (referred to as ‘*Passive*’ strategy).
- An active logic, where the PTO damping coefficients are updated on a wave-by-wave basis (referred to as ‘*Sub-optimal*’ strategy).

A Simulink chart representing the PTO model implemented in WEC-Sim for the ‘*Sub-optimal*’ strategy is illustrated in Figure 3.7. At the inception of a WEC-Sim simulation, the wave input parameters are pre-processed to derive the free-surface elevation time series at the location of the device. The resulting time-series is used to predict the zero up-crossing instants and the period of each passing wave, which in turn informs the selection of the appropriate PTO damping coefficient. The time-series of coefficients is saved in the `pto(1).cdatabase` variable, which is then fed in the PTO model to derive the PTO torque at each instant.

Figure 3.7 Schematic of the MegaRoller PTO WEC-Sim model – Option ‘Sub-optimal’

Note that to convert the linear PTO force to the target torque (shown in Figure 3.6), the damping coefficient in pitch is divided by the square of the lever arm l (i.e. the distance between the bearing axis and the PTO). In future work, the impact of the lever arm length on WEC performance could be assessed (see Section 6).

For the ‘Passive’ strategy, a simple translational PTO block from the WEC-Sim library was used to model the PTO, defining the damping coefficient to apply as the coefficient corresponding to the period of the most energetic sea state in the Peniche site ($T_p = 12.5s$). The damping coefficient in pitch was also divided by l^2 to obtain an equivalent linear damping coefficient.

Initial simulations using each control strategy were conducted to compare the performance of the WEC. The results are shown in Section 5.2.

Noting that the design of the MegaRoller PTO (hydraulic components, e.g. cylinders, manifolds, accumulators, and electrical aspects including the innovative twin drive-train) are the focus of WP2, it is anticipated that the PTO design effort conducted in WP2 will further inform the PTO block in later stages of the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model development.

3.5 Viscous Drag Model

As a first approximation, the drag force acting on the MegaRoller WEC prime mover can be included in the equation of motion and estimated using a Morison based quadratic term:

$$F_d = -\frac{1}{2} C_d \rho A_d \dot{X} |\dot{X}| \tag{1}$$

with ρ being fluid density, \dot{X} being translational velocity and A_d is the characteristic area normal to the movement.

The drag force information and input data provided by AWE⁴ was given as following:

$$F_d = -\frac{1}{8} C_d \rho w h^4 \dot{X} |\dot{X}| \quad (2)$$

where w is the width of the device (30m) and h its height (10m), and $C_d = 1.7$. Accordingly, the characteristic area normal to the movement A_d can be calculated as:

$$A_d = \frac{1}{4} w h^4 \quad (3)$$

Table 3.2 summarises the characteristic area A_d used for the calculation of drag force, along with the drag coefficient C_d used in the simulations.

Table 3.2 Key geometric and mass properties of the MegaRoller WEC prime mover (flap)

Property	Value
Drag coefficient (C_d)	1.7
Characteristic area (A_d) (m ⁵)	75,000

In WEC-Sim's original formulation, the translational velocity in Equation (1) is taken as the global velocity of the hydrodynamic body. However, such approach neglects a potentially significant component of the wave-structure interaction problem, as fluid itself is displaced. Therefore, an updated formulation was implemented that uses the relative velocity between the body and the surrounding fluid. A correction was added to WEC-Sim's hydrodynamic body class to introduce this more advanced formulation. At each time step, the wave orbital velocities are calculated based on the input wave spectrum (in the absence of the hydrodynamic body), and the relative velocity is then calculated by subtracting the wave orbital velocity from hydrodynamic body velocity.

Future work may introduce further complexity to Equation (3) via e.g. the use of non-constant C_d estimates – see also Section 6.

3.6 Slap and Slam Forces Model

As described in [D1.1, 2018], slap and slam are physical phenomena that occur due to the sudden retardation of a volume of fluid, being usually associated to events that involve sudden wave impacts on the surface of a body, or when a body suddenly enters the water at significant speed. In general, slam refers to events when the body hits the free-surface on a plane parallel to the mean free-surface (e.g. body falling into undisturbed water), while slap refers to events when the water hits the body on a plane approximately perpendicular to the wave propagation direction. The consideration of slap and slam forces may be relevant when attempting to improve the fidelity of load estimates on floating bodies in aggressive environmental conditions.

⁴ Vuorinen, M. (2018) [1072] MEGAROLLER WP1 - WEC-Sim model: pre-validation and verification input. [E-mail] Message to: Laporte Weywada, P. 23/05/2018.

An empirical correction to implement the effect of slam and slap forces in WEC-Sim is described in [D1.1, 2018]. The implementation allows the estimation of the pressure distribution over the body during slam and slap events. In a first approximation, and in alignment with DNVGL-RP-C205 [DNV GL, 2017], the formulation implemented assumes that the local slam and slap forces applicable to a body panel at the instant of the impact are proportional to the square of the relative velocity between the body and the fluid, via a non-dimensional space averaged pressure coefficient C_{pa} . Noting that data in DNVGL-RP-C205 relates to simplified geometries, an average pressure coefficient of $C_{pa} = 21.28$ was initially used based on data related to a plate-like structure (see Section 8.7.2.8 and Figure 8-10 of DNVGL-RP-C205).

3.7 Structural Dynamics Model

By default, WEC-Sim follows a rigid-body approach to estimate the dynamic response of a WEC system, where each body is treated as a point mass with mass and inertia properties. To allow deformation of the MegaRoller flap, which in turn may influence the loads calculation, a structural dynamics module was developed and implemented. The module incorporates a finite-element (FE) representation of the MegaRoller flap and enables coupled hydro-elastic assessments.

In order to assess the stiffness of the MegaRoller prime mover flap, an outline structural design was assumed based on the values provided in Table 3.1 and further engineering judgement, assuming the flap consists of a number of outer panels, horizontal stiffeners and vertical stiffeners. Table 3.3 displays the key properties of the structural model.

A simplified FE model for use in the coupled assessment was created using 3D solid elements, as illustrated in Figure 3.3. The stiffness of these elements was calibrated against a separate FE shell model, giving the flap approximately the same stiffness as the assumed structural design. The structural model used a Rayleigh approximation to approximate the structural damping, whereby the structural damping matrix is calculated as a linear combination of the mass and stiffness matrices multiplied by the coefficients α and β respectively. Future work could seek to refine this data as the design progresses (see also Section 6).

Table 3.3 Structural model properties

Property	Value
Material	Steel
Young’s modulus [GPa]	210
Poisson’s ratio [-]	0.3
Panel thickness [mm]	25
Structural damping	$\alpha = 0.001, \beta = 0.2$

Code_Aster [EDF, 2019] was used as the FE solver. When the WEC-Sim structural dynamics module is activated, the FE model is solved at each time step of the simulation, as illustrated in Figure 3.8. At each time step, distributed loads are calculated in WEC-Sim and mapped onto the FE model as nodal forces. The flap was fixed in all degrees-of-freedom (except pitch) at the locations of the two bearings (see Figure 3.3). Two additional point loads were also applied at the PTO interfaces (see Figure 3.3) to represent the loads applied to the flap by the PTOs.

Code_Aster’s dynamic solver (‘DYNA_NON_LINE’) was used to calculate the displacement and velocity response of the flap at each time step. The distributed displacement and velocity results at key interfaces

(e.g. at the PTO connections) are then fed back into WEC-Sim and used to update the loads calculations at the next time step, overriding the default rigid-body predictions.

Figure 3.8 Schematic of the coupling procedure used to interface between WEC-Sim and the structural dynamics module

The hydro-elastic coupling allows structural deformation of the flap to influence the loads calculation. This is particularly relevant in cases of e.g. asymmetrical distribution of deformations across the flap that can potentially lead to uneven loads between the two PTOs. However, the method still relies on rigid-body hydrodynamic coefficients and cannot, for example, update the diffraction force coefficients based on the deformed shape of the flap. Future work (see Section 6) could implement a more complex methodology e.g. by extending the database of hydrodynamic coefficients, similar to that described in Section 3.3, to include different deformed shapes.

The development of the structural dynamics model is further documented in a conference paper [Scriven, 2019], submitted to the 2019 European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC). This paper also presents results from a preliminary case study which found that the PTO loads can be affected by the choice of structural materials. Future work could seek to further investigate the possibility of using structural flexibility to reduce PTO loading, looking at potential implications to both ultimate and fatigue load limits.

3.8 Wave Input

Historically, monochromatic (regular) or unidirectional (irregular) waves have been used in hydraulic models of coastal projects. In the original formulation of WEC-Sim (v3.0), the irregular waves are approximated to a linear superposition of regular waves of distinct amplitudes and directions, and are characterised in the frequency-domain by a wave spectrum. The general form of the unidirectional wave spectra $S(f)$ available in WEC-Sim is given by:

$$S(f) = Af^{-5} \exp(-Bf^{-4}) \quad (4)$$

where f is the frequency (in Hz), and A and B are coefficients that vary depending on the wave spectrum. Standard shape spectra available in WEC-Sim include the Pierson-Moskowitz (PM) spectrum, the two-parameter Bretschneider spectrum (BS) or the Joint North Sea Wave Project, JONSWAP (JS), spectrum.

However, the directional properties of an incoming sea state may also affect the WEC response. In particular, the directional spreading of an input wave may affect the distribution of the wave-induced loads along the MegaRoller WEC flap and the WEC performance. To enable the consideration of realistic, short-crested ocean waves, a directional spreading function was implemented to mimic the spread / diffusion of wave energy over many directions about a mean incoming direction. In a stochastic approach (random phase assumption), the directional wave spectrum $S(f, \beta)$ can be modelled parametrically as the product of the wave spectrum $S(f)$ by an angular spreading function $D(f, \beta)$, leading to:

$$S(f, \beta) = S(f)D(f, \beta) \quad (5)$$

The formulation of $D(f, \beta)$ must ensure that the total energy in the directional spectrum is the same as the total energy in the corresponding one-dimensional spectrum, i.e.:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} S(f)D(f, \beta) d\beta df = \int_0^{\infty} S(f)df \quad (6)$$

In a preliminary step, a simple idealised cosine-squared spreading function $D(\beta)$ was implemented in WEC-Sim:

$$D(\beta) = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{\pi} \cos^2(\beta - \beta_0) & \text{for } |\beta - \beta_0| < \frac{\pi}{2} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where β_0 is the direction of the incoming wave(s).

Simulations comparing WEC-Sim outputs in terms of WEC performance in a unidirectional and multidirectional input wave fields are presented in Section 5.

4 DESIGN LOAD CASE DEFINITION AND PRIORITISATION

4.1 Overview

In this section, a rationale for the prioritisation of the DLCs in the load characterisation effort of the MegaRoller project is detailed. Overall, the selection of the DLCs aims to prioritise design situations that are likely to affect the primary design of the MegaRoller WEC, in particular the design of the PTO.

An assessment of the most relevant design standards and guidelines, conducted in the context of Task 6.6 [D6.6, 2019], is summarised in Section 4.2. The DLC prioritisation process is initiated in Section 4.3 with a description of the environmental conditions at the proposed deployment site in Peniche (Section 4.3.1), which are subsequently synthesised into a format suitable for immediate coupling with the proposed DLCs (Section 4.3.2). Finally, a risk analysis of the failure modes affecting the WEC is summarised in Section 4.4, based on the generic risk analysis for a hydraulic PTO conducted under the SDWED project [SDWED, 2014].

To conclude this section, a table summarising the priority DLCs is presented in Section 4.5, along with a detailed calculation guide for the load characterisation exercise. In general, the high-level DLC descriptions listed in [WES, 2016] are used throughout this section.

4.2 Key Standards and Guidelines: Characteristic Loads

In this sub-section, design standards relevant to the activities conducted in the MegaRoller project are overviewed. Emphasis is given to guidance directly relevant to the load characterisation activities; further design standards and design principles are reviewed in [D6.6, 2019]. At present, there are no dedicated standards for the design of WECs. As a direct consequence, there is limited experience in defining design situations and DLCs for any WEC type. High-level documents that approach WEC design and certification include:

- i. IEC TS 62600-2:2016 Marine Energy – Wave, Tidal and Other Water Converters; Part 2: Design Requirements for Marine Energy Systems. [IEC, 2016].
- ii. Wave Energy Scotland (WES) ‘Structural Forces and Stresses for Wave Energy Devices – Landscaping Study’, 2016. [WES, 2016].
- iii. Det Norske Veritas AS (DNV) Offshore Service Specification (OSS) 312 ‘Certification of Tidal and Wave Energy Converters’ (DNV-OSS-312) October 2008 (Amended April 2012). Provides an overview the principles and procedures associated with the certification of WECs. It does not include technical provisions. [DNV, 2008].
- iv. DNV’s ‘Guidelines on Design and Operation of Wave Energy Converters’, May 2005, The Carbon Trust. This document compiles a list of related standards and outlines methodologies for fatigue analysis (Appendix A) and wave load modelling (Appendix B). [DNV, 2005].
- v. The European Marine Energy Centre (EMEC) ‘Guidelines for Design Basis of Marine Energy Conversion Systems’, 2009. Provides an overview of general aspects behind design basis documentation, covering both wave and tidal energy converters. [EMEC, 2009].

Additionally, Table 4.1 provides a shortlist of key documentation from the maritime, oil & gas and offshore wind sectors that are potentially relevant to WEC design due to the extent of the similarities in the structural design of these structures. Overall, and as in [WES, 2016], the listed documents were used in the present load characterisation effort as a starting point when defining DLCs.

Table 4.1 Core documentation: WEC load and structural analysis and WEC design process

Doc. Reference	Application / Relevance	Supporting / Additional Documents
Bureau Veritas NI 631 Certification scheme for Marine Renewable Energy Technologies (2016)	Guidance note on certification schemes relevant to marine renewable energy technologies	DNVGL-SE-0477 (2017) (replaced DNV-OSS-304) Risk Based Verification of Offshore Structures
DNVGL-RP-C205 (2017) Environmental Conditions and Environmental Loads	Overall description of environmental conditions and design loads (environmental, permanent, functional and accidental), including principles for structural design	DNVGL-OS-C103 (2015) (replaced DNV-OS-C103) Structural Design of Column Stabilised Units (LRFD Method) DNVGL-RP-C204 (2017) Design against Accidental Loads API RP 2FPS (2011) Recommended Practice for Planning, Designing, and Constructing Floating Production Systems
DNVGL-ST-C501 (2017) Composite Components DNVGL-OS-C101 (2016) Design of offshore steel structures, general – LRFD method	Structural design and analysis (primary composite and steel design, respectively) Strength analysis in FEM	GL Rules and Guidelines IV-6-4 (2007) Offshore Technology - Structural Design GL Rules and Guidelines IV-2-5 (2012) Guideline for the Certification of Offshore Wind Turbines - Strength Analyses DNVGL-RU-SHIP-Pt2Ch3 (2015) Materials and Welding – Non-Metallic Materials DNVGL-RU-SHIP-Pt2Ch2 (2018) Materials and Welding – Metallic Materials
ABS Pub# 115 (2018) Guide for Fatigue Assessment of Offshore Structures	Overview of fatigue assessment methods in offshore installations (inc. safety factors)	DNVGL-CG-0129 (2015) Fatigue Assessment of Ship Structures DNVGL-OS-C102 (2018) Structural design of offshore ship-shaped units
DNV-RP-A201 (2014) Document Types – Definitions	Quantitative reliability assessment	API RP 17N (2017), Recommended Practice for Subsea Production System reliability and Technical Risk Management BS 5760 (2014) Reliability of systems, equipment and components ISO 14224 (2016) Petroleum and gas industries - Collection and exchange of reliability and maintenance data for equipment. ISO 2394 (2015) General Principles on Reliability for Structures
DNVGL-RP-A203 (2017) Qualification of New Technology	Technology qualification	DNVGL-SE-0160 (2015) Technology qualification management and verification

4.3 Environmental Conditions

4.3.1 Overview

The objective of this sub-section is to define the site-specific environmental conditions to consider when estimating the environmental loads acting on a WEC, for a range of relevant design situations (e.g. power production, parked / survival etc.). In short, a characterisation of the long-term metocean conditions at the target deployment site in Peniche (Portugal) is presented.

4.3.1.1 Wave Climate

To define long-term representative conditions at the Peniche site, environmental site data provided by AWE from SWAN was processed. The data provided (see footnote 2) covers the period between January 1997 and December 2006, i.e. 10 years. The data consists of 6-hour averages of significant wave height H_s , energy period T_e , mean direction of wave propagation, peak period T_p , mean wave periods T_{m01} and T_{m02} , and the wind speed and direction.

Figure 4.1 illustrates the location of the Peniche site in Western Europe. The coordinates of the data point are 39.4N and 9.3E, which corresponds to a location estimated to be in the 12m depth contour. Using the full 10-year dataset, long-term wave statistics were derived. These are presented in Figure 4.2 to Figure 4.6, and include:

- Probability of occurrence of each H_s, T_p pair (long term average) – Figure 4.2.
- Directional spectra – Figure 4.3.
- Environmental contours (long-term return periods) – Figure 4.4 and Figure 4.5.
- Probability of exceedance (for relevant spectral parameters) – Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.1 Location of the Peniche site in Western Europe⁵ – site location indicated by the red point on the west coast of Portugal (coordinates 39.4N, 9.3W)

⁵ From K2 Management in-house offshore resource database.

Figure 4.2 Probability of occurrence of each H_s, T_p pair (39.4N, 9.3W, Jan 1997 – Dec 2006)

As evidenced in Figure 4.2, the largest proportion of occurrences can be observed in the [5s, 14s] peak period range, for significant wave heights between 0.5m and 4.5m. These results can be used when defining the normal and reduced normal sea states (*NSS* and *RNSS*, respectively), following [WES, 2016] – see also Section 4.3.2.

Figure 4.3 Directional wave spectra (39.4N, 9.3W, Jan 1997 – Dec 2006)

Figure 4.3 shows that the direction of wave propagation is predominantly spread over about 40° around the North-West direction, which is consistent with the typical conditions for the western Portuguese coastline.

Regarding extreme sea state (*ESS*) conditions, these can be defined using environmental contours, where each contour represents the extreme conditions for a given return period. The environmental contours were determined for 1-year and 50-year return periods based on the Inverse First-Order Reliability method (I-FORM) approach, following [Eckert-Gallup et al., 2016]. A modified version of Extreme Sea

State Contour module of the WDRT⁶ toolbox was used. An assessment of the quality of the fit of multiple probability density functions (PDF) was completed and is illustrated in Figure 4.4. In Figure 4.5, the 1-year and 50-year return period contours derived using the generalised extreme value distribution are shown, as this was identified as the PDF leading to the best fit.

Figure 4.4 Environmental contour characterisation: H_s - T_p scatter diagram of data with 1-year environmental contours for multiple probability density functions (39.4N, 9.3W, Jan 1997 – Dec 2006)

Figure 4.5 Environmental contour characterisation: H_s - T_p scatter diagram of data with 1-year and 50-year environmental contours (39.4N, 9.3W, Jan 1997 – Dec 2006)

⁶ <http://wec-sim.github.io/WDRT/modules.html#module-WDRT.ESSC>

Figure 4.6 Exceedance plots (39.4N, 9.3W, Jan 1997 – Dec 2006): H_s (top), T_p (middle), Wave power (bottom)

Finally, high-level metrics can be obtained from Figure 4.6, which illustrates that e.g. there is a 75% probability of not exceeding a significant wave height of 2.285m, a peak period of 12.78s and an incident wave power flux of 26.28kW/m.

Other items may be required to fully describe the wave climate of the site, such as local effects (e.g. site-specific spectral shapes) and individual wave considerations. For the latter, focused wave groups (*FWGs*) may be considered for specific DLCs (if relevant). Following [WES, 2016], and where applicable, *FWGs* will be defined to have a height corresponding to the most probable maximum wave height value for each sea state, following DNVGL-RP-C205 (Sect. 3.7.3.5).

4.3.1.2 Water Levels

Estimates of the 1-year and 50-year water level at the target site are presented in Table 4.2. The data listed in Table 4.2 was provided by AWE⁷.

Table 4.2 Definition of water levels for the target site

Water level	Value*
Astronomical Tide	Lowest (LAT) = -1.80m Highest (HAT) = 1.88m
1-year return period	min = -1.85m max = 1.95m
50-year return period	min = -2.00m max = 2.18m

* All values are related to the mean water level

4.3.1.3 Other Environmental Conditions

Additional environmental conditions that may be relevant to characterise the target deployment site include:

- Marine growth.
- Currents.
- Wind.

In general terms, marine growth refers to a surface coat on marine structures, caused by plants, animals and bacteria, potentially affecting inertial loads, geometry and the surface roughness of the WEC. In [DNV GL, 2007] it is recommended that in preparation for load calculation exercises “*all structural members, conductors, risers and appurtenances shall be increased in cross-sectional area to account for marine growth thickness*”. Should marine growth be relevant for any of the critical design situations to be identified in Section 4.5, suitable DLCs will include marine growth allowances. The NORSOK standard N-003 provides recommendations regarding marine growth.

⁷ M. Vuorinen (2018), *Water levels for the design load cases*, [E-mail] message to P. Laporte-Weywada, dated 21/09/2018

Given the preliminary stage of the design, in a first step marine growth will not be considered, assuming that regular cleaning is planned. It is recommended that this assumption is revisited in more advanced design stages.

Finally, Figure 4.7 shows the current rose at the Peniche site⁸. The maximum velocity is below 0.7m/s.

Figure 4.7 Current rose at the Peniche site – velocity in m/s

Given the low current speed present at the site, the effect of currents will not be considered in the loading characterisation effort conducted in this report. This assumption may be revisited in more advanced design stages.

Finally, it should be noted that the MegaRoller WEC is designed with a very limited freeboard. Therefore, the effects of wind may be neglected for a selection of design load conditions.

4.3.2 Definition of Environmental Condition Metrics

Details of the environmental condition metrics of the proposed site are given in this sub-section. The data described in Section 4.3.1 is synthesised into a format suitable for immediate coupling with DLCs by defining metrics such as normal sea states (*NSS*) and extreme sea states (*ESS*).

The nomenclature associated with the environmental condition metrics can be found in e.g. [WES, 2016]. Figure 4.8 defines the environmental contours, using a contour approach. In such approach, a reduced number of samples are taken from each environmental contour to allow an initial, priority assessment to be completed. Alternatively, in future work, a full environmental approach may be also used, where a large number of samples (c. 200) are taken within the 100-year contour – see Section 6.

⁸ M. Vuorinen (2018), *Current data and bearing locations*, [E-mail] message to P. Laporte-Weywada, dated 24/10/2018

Figure 4.8 Detailed environmental characterisation: contour-based samples from the 1-year and 50-year contours (39.4N, 9.3W, Jan 1997 – Dec 2006)

The target values related to the metrics, such as H_s and T_p , are presented in Table 4.3. Regarding the metrics, the following notes are relevant when defining the methodology for load analysis:

- i. The range of H_s , T_p combinations considered for both *NSS* and *ESS* is restricted by the wave breaking criteria (steepness and depth limitations).
- ii. A standard spectral shape (JONSWAP) is assumed for all combinations of significant wave height and wave period. If relevant, additional effects such as those related to e.g. spectral shape may be addressed at later design stages.
- iii. It is important to acknowledge that the loads will, in addition to wave height and period, be primarily sensitive to wave directionality, and potentially the phasing of wave groups. In [WES, 2016], it is recommended that the variability of parameters derived for the load analysis is checked under simulations with the same spectral density and different sets of random phases and directions.
 - a. As a first approximation, different sets of wave angles and spread will be considered in DLC 1.1, using the most energetic sea state at the Peniche site (i.e. H_s of 2.25m and T_p of 12.5s) as a representation of the reduced set of normal sea states (*RNSS*).
 - b. The full set of normal sea states (*NSS*) will be considered in DLC 1.1 with different control strategies and spreading configurations, and for one wave angle (normal to the flap).
 - c. Both fatigue and ultimate loads will be considered.
- iv. Design situations that may lead to high, short-term loading patterns affecting the prime mover (e.g. slamming or slapping) can be assessed using representative environmental metrics (e.g. *FWG* and / or *Regular Waves, RW*) that synthesise events related to *ESS*, following [WES, 2016]. A *FWG* approach will be considered in DLCs 1.4 and 2.1.
- v. The water level considerations listed in Table 4.3 follow the recommendations provided in Section 4.3.1. As a first approximation, and in agreement with AWE⁹, DLC 1.4 will assess the impact of slap and slam forces at different water levels to investigate the loading envelope associated with high load, transient driven events.

⁹ P. Laporte-Weywada, *WP1 discussions – Load characterisation effort and required inputs*, [internal memo], dated 31/10/2018.

- vi. Given the (low) magnitude of the current velocity the priority DLCs will only consider wave loading.
- vii. Items such as temperatures (sea and air) or salinity may affect specific material options and can therefore be more relevant in advanced stages of the MegaRoller WEC design process. Finally, the effects of other environmental conditions (e.g. ice) can be neglected due to the site characteristics.

The target values presented in Table 4.3 were applied to the original DLC table presented in [WES, 2016] as described in Section 4.5 to reflect the proposed approach.

Table 4.3 Definition of environmental condition metrics for the target site

Environmental Condition Metric	Target Values				Notes
NSS	H_s (m)		T_p (s)		Where applicable: [Start_Value:Step:End_Value] In total: 80 sea states evaluated (covering c. 98% of occurrences) Wave angle varies between 0° (normal to the flap) and 15°. Directional spread (when considered) follows spread function described in Section 3.8.
	0.75:0.5:4.25		4.5:1:15.5		
RNSS	H_s (m)		T_p (s)		Most energetic sea state at the Peniche site.
	2.25		12.5		
ESS	H_{S1}		H_{S50}		ESS for 100-year return period also identified.
	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	
	1.61	5.54	2.14	5.54	
	2.29	6.64	2.83	6.64	
	2.94	7.75	3.52	7.75	
	3.56	8.86	4.21	8.86	
	4.16	9.96	4.90	9.96	
	4.73	11.1	5.58	11.1	
	5.24	12.2	6.21	12.2	
	5.64	13.3	6.78	13.3	
5.88	14.4	7.20	14.4		
5.81	15.5	7.35	15.5		
5.10	16.6	6.98	16.6		
FWG	Target H_s (m)		Target T_p (s)		Largest waves within ESS – H_{S1} .
	5.88m		14.4s		
Extreme Water Level	min = -2.00m max = 2.18m				50-year return period water level. Values are relative to the mean water level.
Wave Angle	min = -15° mean = 0° max = +15°				Wave angle refers to the incidence on the panel – a 0° wave angle means a direction of propagation perpendicular to the flap.

4.4 Risk Assessment: FMEA Matrices

In [SDWED, 2014] a detailed risk assessment for a range of generic WECs was conducted, in an effort to generate generic guidance to support the WEC design effort without compromising on safety and integrity.

Failure modes related to strength and fatigue (high-cycle) limit states were identified for the MegaRoller PTO, and a range of DLCs suggested to address potential causes of failure. The relevant FMEA matrices are provided in Appendix D of [SDWED, 2014]. The most common failure modes and failure mechanisms from the FMEA matrices provided in [SDWED, 2014] related to PTO loading are summarised in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Risk analysis for a generic hydraulic PTO – most common failure mode and mechanisms – based on [SDWED, 2014]

Item	Most common failure mode / mechanism	Risk ranking*
Valve	Failure to function on demand	16
	Leakage	16
Centrifugal pump	External leakage	20
	Mechanical failure	20
Reciprocating pump / motor	Leakage (internal, external)	20
	Mechanical failure	20
Hydraulic filter	Blocked filter	20
	Fail to clean	20
Hydraulic accumulator (bladder)	Pressure loss	20
	Jammed valve	20
Hydraulic accumulator (piston)	Leakage	20
	Jammed valve / piston	16
Hydraulic actuator	Jamming	16
	Excessive side load	20

* On a scale from 1 to 25: 1 is low probability, minor consequence; 25 is high risk, critical consequence.

Overall, and as a preliminary step, DLCs considering a fault leading to a locked PTO will be considered. In future work, more detailed modelling of potential fault scenarios and dominant load cases could be considered based on updated design parameters, such as customised control strategies (see Section 6). In particular, the detailed FMEA table generated as part of WP5 could be used to refine the selection of representative fault conditions.

4.5 Shortlist of DLCs

4.5.1 Overview

Codes of best practice such as Section 7.3.1 of IEC-TS 62600-2 [IEC, 2016] state that structural integrity can be calculated from the following combinations:

- Normal design situations and normal external (environmental) conditions.
- Normal design situations and extreme external conditions.
- Fault design situations and appropriate external conditions.
- Design situations for transportation, installation and maintenance, and the appropriate external conditions.

By definition, a DLC is a combination of environmental conditions coupled with the state of the WEC (control state, fault conditions etc.). Table 4.5 summarises the shortlisted DLCs for the MegaRoller project that address the key aspects overviewed throughout Sections 2 to 4 of this report.

The DLCs shortlisted focus on design situations that are likely to affect the primary design of the MegaRoller WEC, and that in turn can be directly associated with the design of the PTO. These were selected based on a review of the FMEA matrix (see Section 4.4) and through discussions with AWE⁹. In DLC 1.1, the analysis focuses on sea states that contribute significantly to the mean annual energy production (MAEP). In particular, variations ‘a’ and ‘b’ consider the impact of the novel control algorithm, where the damping force is optimised on a wave-by-wave basis, compared to a traditional control algorithm, where the damping remains constant throughout the sea state. Furthermore, the most energetic sea state at the Peniche site, defined by $(H_s, T_p) = (2.25\text{m}, 12.5\text{s})$ is considered for further loads assessment. Variation ‘c’ aims to assess the WEC loading under different wave angles, in unidirectional and spread waves.

In DLC 1.4, an investigation of the importance of the slap and slam forces in the loading envelope is conducted. The investigations also consider the impact of tidal range, using the extreme water levels presented in Table 4.2. The environmental conditions are represented using a *FWG* defined based on the 1-year return period with the highest significant wave height $(H_s, T_p) = (5.88\text{m}, 14.4\text{s})$. Assuming that 1,000 waves are present in a 3-hour storm (average period of 10s), the maximum wave height can be estimated by:

$$H_{FWG} = F_H(h)^{1000} = \left\{ 1 - e^{-2\left(\frac{h}{H_s}\right)^2} \right\} \cong 1.9 * H_s$$

It is noted that, although the DLC uses a sea state on the 1-year environmental contour, the *FWG* wave height (11.17m) appears very high with regard to the low water level – modifications to the guidance issued in [WES, 2016] may be required to address such extreme situations.

A range of seeds for the wave phase are considered, varying the location of the highest individual wave. The 10-, 50- and 100-year characteristic value of the PTO load, slap and slam forces are estimated.

For DLC 2.1, a fault event in the control system during power production is considered, where the damping coefficient for one PTO is erroneously set to a high value. The 10-, 50- and 100-year characteristic value of the PTO load is derived from simulations considering a range of wave seeds.

Finally, in DLC 7.1, an assessment of the loading related to the 11 sea states that define *ESS* – H_{s1} is conducted. The sea state leading to the highest PTO loads is then selected for additional investigations, including the calculation of the 10-, 50- and 100-year characteristic value of the PTO load.

The following abbreviations are used in Table 4.5:

<i>NSS</i>	Normal Operational Sea States
<i>RNSS</i>	Reduced Range Normal Operational Sea States
<i>FWG</i>	Focused Wave Group
<i>ESS</i>	Extreme Operational Sea States
H_{s1}	Significant wave height with a recurrence period of 1 year
U	Ultimate strength analysis

F Fatigue strength analysis

Table 4.5 Shortlist of DLCs: summary calculation guide

Design Situation	DLC	Wave Conditions	PTO Conditions	Additional Conditions	Type of Analysis
1. Power production	1.1	<i>NSS</i> <i>RNSS</i>	Power production	Variations: a. Passive control b. Sub-optimal control c. Oblique and spread waves	U
	1.4	<i>FWG</i>	Power production	Slap / slam load investigations. Influence of tidal range.	U
2. Power production plus occurrence of fault	2.1	<i>FWG</i>	Power production	Fault in control system(s)	U
7. Parked plus occurrence of fault	7.1	<i>ESS – H_{s1}</i>	Parked	Fault condition	U

4.5.2 Detailed Calculation Guide

Load case tables are provided in this sub-section. Each table aims to describe the case name, the environmental conditions (significant wave height, peak period, wave angle, directional spreading, water depth), the control strategy applied and the simulation conditions (linear or nonlinear Froude-Krylov and buoyancy forces formulation). The simulation file name key is *x.x_htdsw_c_l*, where:

<i>x.x</i>	DLC number
<i>h</i>	<i>H_s</i>
<i>t</i>	<i>T_p</i>
<i>d</i>	wave direction
<i>s</i>	spreading parameter
<i>w</i>	water depth
<i>c</i>	control strategy
<i>l</i>	linear or nonlinear Froude-Krylov option

Table 4.6 Description of the DLC 1.1 simulations: detailed calculation guide

Design situation:	Power production
Design Load Case:	1.1
Wave conditions:	Normal sea state (NSS), Reduced normal sea state (RNSS)
PTO conditions:	Power production
Type of analysis	Ultimate

Description of the simulations

Name	Wave conditions				Control strategy	Other condition
	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	θ (deg)	Spread		
1.1_aaaa_a_a ~ 1.1_hlaaa_a_a	0.75 - 4.25	4.5 - 15.5	0	0	Passive	Linear
1.1_aaaa_b_a ~ 1.1_hlaaa_b_a	0.75 - 4.25	4.5 - 15.5	0	0	Sub-optimal	Linear
1.1_aaaba_b_a ~ 1.1_hlaba_b_a	0.75 - 4.25	4.5 - 15.5	0	1	Sub-optimal	Linear
1.1_diaa_b_b ~ 1.1_didaa_b_b	2.25	12.5	0° to +15°	0	Sub-optimal	Nonlinear

Comments

- Normal sea states with irregular waves defined using JONSWAP spectrum with $\gamma = 3.3$.
- '0' and '1' in the 'spread' condition mean unidirectional and spread waves, respectively.
- 'Nonlinear' refers to the weakly nonlinear approach implemented for the calculation of the buoyancy and Froude-Krylov forces.
- 'Linear' refers to the linear model where the buoyancy and Froude-Krylov forces are calculated using the BEM calculated linear wave-excitation and hydrostatic coefficients.
- 'Passive' control strategy refers to the logic where the PTO damping coefficients remain unchanged throughout each sea state.
- 'Sub-optimal' control strategy refers to the logic where the PTO damping coefficients are updated on a wave-by-wave basis.
- Water depth: 12m.

Table 4.7 Description of the DLC 1.4 simulations: detailed calculation guide

Design situation:	Power production
Design Load Case:	1.4
Wave conditions:	Focused wave group (FWG)
PTO conditions:	Power production
Type of analysis	Ultimate

Description of the simulations

Name	Wave conditions				Control strategy	Other condition
	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	θ (deg)	Spread		
1.4_aaaa_a_a_1 ~ 1.4_aaaa_a_a_100	5.88	14.4	0	0	Passive	Water depth 10m
1.4_aaab_a_a_1 ~ 1.4_aaab_a_a_100	5.88	14.4	0	0	Passive	Water depth 14m

Comments

- Simulations use the nonlinear approach for the buoyancy and Froude-Krylov forces.
- Focused wave group built using 100 different phase seeds.
- Empirical correction for slap and slam forces included ($C_{pa} = 21.28$)
- Target sea state for the focused wave group is $(H_s, T_p) = (5.88m, 14.4s)$, leading to $H_{FWG} \cong 11.17m$.

Table 4.8 Description of the DLC 2.1 simulations: detailed calculation guide

Design situation:	Power production plus occurrence of fault
Design Load Case:	2.1
Wave conditions:	Focused wave group (FWG)
PTO conditions:	Power production
Type of analysis	Ultimate

Description of the simulations

Name	Wave conditions				Control strategy	Other condition
	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	θ (deg)	Spread		
2.1_aaaaa_a_a_1 ~ 2.1_aaaaa_a_a_100	5.88	14.4	0	0	Passive	Nonlinear

Comments

- Fault condition: PTO2 jammed, high damping applied.
- Fault persistent throughout the simulation.
- Focused wave group built using 100 different phase seeds.
- Target sea state for the focused wave group is $(H_s, T_p) = (5.88\text{m}, 14.4\text{s})$, leading to $H_{FWG} \cong 11.17\text{m}$.
- Water depth: 12m.

Table 4.9 Description of the DLC 7.1 simulations: detailed calculation guide

Design situation:	Parked plus occurrence of fault
Design Load Case:	7.1
Wave conditions:	Extreme sea state – 1-year return period (ESS- H_{s1})
PTO conditions:	Parked
Type of analysis	Ultimate

Description of the simulations

Name	Wave conditions				Control strategy	Other condition
	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	θ (deg)	Spread		
7.1_aaaaa_a_a ~ 7.1_kkaaa_a_a	1.61- 5.10	5.5- 16.6	0	0	Passive	Linear
7.1_iiaaa_a_b	5.88	14.4	0	0	Passive	Nonlinear

Comments

- Fault condition: PTO2 jammed, high damping applied.
- Fault persistent throughout the simulation.
- Parked condition: PTO disconnected, no damping applied (for PTO1).
- Initial screening considers sea states sampled on the 1-year environmental contour target.
- Detailed load analysis conducted for the sea state leading to the highest PTO loads: $(H_s, T_p) = (5.88\text{m}, 14.4\text{s})$.
- Water depth: 12m.

5 LOAD ANALYSIS RESULTS

5.1 Overview

Following the prioritisation of the DLCs presented in Section 4, the load calculations have focused on four DLCs: DLC 1.1 and DLC 1.4 (Power production), DLC 2.1 (Power production with fault) and DLC 7.1 (Parked with fault).

The next sub-sections introduce initial results from the load and structural models presented in Section 3. In Section 5.2, the results of preliminary investigations on the load model are presented. In Section 5.3, initial results for a range key metrics considered are described for each priority DLC.

5.2 Initial Investigations

Prior to conducting the load analysis exercise for the priority DLCs (see also Section 4.5), preliminary investigations were conducted. The preliminary assessment, documented in Section 5.2.1, focused on the influence of the control strategy on WEC performance, to estimate the potential benefits of a wave-by-wave control strategy. In Sections 5.2.2 and 5.2.3, two additional features of the WEC-Sim model are investigated, namely the use of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients and directional spreading, respectively, to assess their impact on the WEC's response.

5.2.1 Influence of Control Strategy on WEC Performance

To assess the potential benefits of a wave-by-wave control strategy, where the PTO settings are optimised for each incoming wave, the WEC performance outputs using the '*Sub-optimal*' control option (see Section 3.4) were compared to those obtained following a passive strategy, where the PTO damping coefficient is constant throughout the sea state ('*Passive*').

For each control strategy ('*Passive*' and '*Sub-optimal*'), a total of 96 simulations were initially conducted, considering sea states with significant wave heights varying between 0.75m and 4.25m (0.5m step) and peak periods varying between 4.5s and 15.5s (1s step).

Figure 5.1 shows the resulting power matrix for each control strategy ('*Passive*', left; and '*Sub-optimal*', right). An average improvement can be seen between the '*Passive*' control strategy and the '*Sub-optimal*' strategy, in particular around the higher values of wave height and mid-range peak periods, where the improvements are more significant. The ratio of power matrices shows that the improvement is primarily related to the wave peak period (Figure 5.2): as the peak period of the sea state moves closer to the peak period of the most energetic sea state, which was used to select the damping coefficient for the '*Passive*' strategy, the improvement becomes less significant.

Figure 5.1 Power matrix for the ‘Passive’ (left) and ‘Sub-optimal’ (right) control strategies

Figure 5.2 Influence of the peak period on the improvement in absorbed power: Ratio of ‘Sub-optimal’ power matrix by ‘Passive’ power matrix

It should be noted that a similar pattern is also observed for the PTO loads, with the ratio of root-mean-square (RMS) PTO force ranging approximately between 0.5 and 4.5. Effectively, this implies that the improvement in power absorption when changing control strategy is dominantly carried out by an increase in the PTO loading, whilst the pitch velocity remains fairly similar between control strategies. Such observation may be further investigated in later stages (see Section 6), e.g. by examining the time-series of the relevant variables.

To assess the overall impact of the control strategies in WEC performance, the Mean Annual Energy Production (MAEP) was derived using the Peniche site scatter diagram (see Section 4.3.1). The results are summarised in Table 5.1, showing an overall increase of approximately two-fold in terms of MAEP between the ‘Passive’ and the ‘Sub-optimal’ control strategies. Table 5.1 also features the capacity factor of the WEC, derived as the ratio between the MAEP and the rated annual energy yield, assuming a power rating of 1MW. Table 5.1 shows that only the ‘Sub-optimal’ control strategy leads to capacity factor estimates that are more akin to those observed in comparable technologies e.g. offshore wind turbines. Overall, it is shown that control is a decisive factor in WEC performance, and that further optimisation work may be required, considering in more details the influence on the resulting PTO loading profiles.

Table 5.1 Mean Annual Energy Production (MAEP) and capacity factor at the Peniche site for the ‘Passive’ and ‘Sub-optimal’ control strategies

Control strategy	MAEP (GWh/y)	Capacity factor
Passive	0.9	10%
Sub-optimal	1.7	19%

5.2.2 Influence of a Database of Hydrodynamic Coefficients

This sub-section focuses on the impact of using a database of hydrodynamic coefficients (see also Section 3.3) versus the original WEC-Sim formulation, where the hydrodynamic properties are derived solely for the WEC’s mean equilibrium position. In both cases, the simulations were run using the sub-optimal control strategy described in Section 3.4.

Figure 5.3 compares different key performance metrics between the original formulation of WEC-Sim (*‘No database’*) and the novel implementation with the database of hydrodynamic coefficients (*‘Database’*). The metrics consider the mean mechanical absorbed power (a), the RMS of pitch angle (b), the RMS of PTO force (c) and the RMS of PTO velocity (d).

Figure 5.3 Influence of the database formulation on the WEC performance – *‘Database’* vs. *‘No database’*: a) Ratio of power matrices, b) Ratio of RMS pitch angle, c) Ratio of RMS PTO force, d) Ratio of RMS PTO velocity

In sea states with short wave periods and those with longer wave periods and greater significant wave heights, the impact of the database implementation remains limited (up to around 10%) in all the metrics considered. However, an increase of more than 25% can be seen in waves with longer periods and lower significant wave heights, as well as in medium periods and heights.

Observing time-series of pitch motion (Figure 5.4, left) and absorbed power (Figure 5.4, right) for cases displaying a large difference in absorbed power (e.g. $T_p = 11.5s$, $H_s = 1.75m$), it can be seen that higher peaks in pitch angle are observed when using the database option (see e.g. the results around 1380s in Figure 5.4). In turn, the differences in pitch angle influence the mean power estimates, illustrating the potential impact that the database option may have on power production design situations. The potential effects of the resolution of the database may be addressed in future work.

Figure 5.4 Comparison of time-series of motion in pitch (in degree, left) and absorbed power (in kW, right) between the 'No database' (in blue) and 'Database' cases – 80s extract – $T_p = 11.5s$ and $H_s = 1.75m$

To assess the overall impact of the database implementation in the estimated WEC performance, the MAEP for the Peniche site was also derived – see Table 5.2. Overall, a 10% difference can be seen when comparing the MAEP obtained via the original formulation and that associated with a model that includes the database implementation.

Table 5.2 Mean Annual Energy Production (MAEP) and capacity factor at the Peniche site for the WEC-Sim formulations with 'No database' and 'Database'

Control strategy	MAEP (GWh/y)	Capacity factor
<i>No database</i>	1.7	19%
<i>Database</i>	1.9	22%

5.2.3 Influence of the Directional Spreading of the Incoming Wave

This sub-section focuses on the impact of directional spread on different key performance metrics. Figure 5.5 shows the ratio of the mechanically absorbed power output with a simple directional spreading function applied to the wave energy spectrum ('*Spread*') to results when no spread is applied ('*Unidirectional*'). Note that no database of hydrodynamic coefficients was considered in the simulations presented in this sub-section.

Figure 5.5 Influence of the directional spreading on the WEC performance – ‘Spread’ vs. ‘Unidirectional’: Ratio of power matrices

The directional spreading of the incident waves generally leads to a decrease in power performance, with less power absorbed in multidirectional waves compared to unidirectional waves. The reduction is of greater importance in small wave periods (40% decrease at around 5s peak period). Similar to Section 5.2.2, other metrics of interest were analysed including the RMS of pitch motion, the mean PTO force and the RMS of PTO velocity, showing a similar trend to Figure 5.5. The overall decrease in power performance also leads to a decrease in MAEP and capacity factor, as can be seen in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3 Mean Annual Energy Production (MAEP) and capacity factor at the Peniche site in ‘Spread’ and ‘Unidirectional’ waves

Control strategy	MAEP (GWh/y)	Capacity factor
<i>Unidirectional</i>	1.7	19%
<i>Spread</i>	1.4	16%

5.3 Loading Envelope

5.3.1 DLC 1.1 Power Production

In DLC 1.1, the analysis focused on investigating the PTO force and hinge motion experienced by the MegaRoller WEC and PTO for three variations (see also Table 4.5):

- In variation *a*, the control strategy considered is passive, i.e. the same damping coefficient is kept constant throughout the simulation and for all sea states.
- In variation *b*, the control strategy considered is sub-optimal, i.e. the damping coefficient applied is optimised on a wave-by-wave basis.
- In variation *c*, different configurations of angled seas are considered:
 - The full set of *NSS* is considered with directional spreading (variation *c1*).
 - The most energetic sea state is considered with different incident wave angles (variation *c2*).

The following sub-sections present a range of key metrics to estimate the loading (PTO force) and expected hinge motions (pitch angle and velocity) experienced by the MegaRoller WEC and PTO, for the different configurations considered.

5.3.1.1 Variation a: Baseline (Passive control)

In variation *a*, the input waves considered are unidirectional, with an angle of incidence of 0° , and cover the Peniche scatter diagram. The control strategy considered is passive, i.e. the same damping coefficient is kept constant throughout the simulations.

Figure 5.6 shows the peak and RMS values for the pitch angle, PTO force and pitch velocity.

Figure 5.6 Matrices of peak (left column) and RMS (right column) of pitch angle (in degrees, top row), PTO force (for PTO1, in MN, middle row) and pitch velocity (in rad/s, bottom row) – variation *a*

It can be seen that, for high H_s and T_p , the range of motion in pitch increases significantly, with peak angle values of up to more than 70° . This may be critical to the structural integrity of the flap and should be considered in the design.

A similar pattern of overall increase in values with increasing H_s and T_p can also be seen for the PTO force. At high H_s and T_p , the PTO force peaks reach values of around 0.8MN, with a maximum peak value of 1MN – and the RMS PTO force reaches values of up to 0.2MN.

Finally, the pitch velocity remains similar between all the sea states considered, with peak values of around 1rad/s, with RMS values varying between 0.05 to 0.2rad/s.

5.3.1.2 Variation b: Active control (sub-optimal)

In variation *b*, the input waves considered are unidirectional, with an angle of incidence of 0° , and cover the Peniche scatter diagram. The control strategy considered is sub-optimal, i.e. the damping coefficient applied is optimised on a wave-by-wave basis.

Figure 5.7 shows the peak and RMS values for the pitch angle, PTO force and pitch velocity.

Figure 5.7 Matrices of peak (left column) and RMS (right column) of pitch angle (in degrees, top row), PTO force (for PTO1, in MN, middle row) and pitch velocity (in rad/s, bottom row) – variation *b*

When moving to a sub-optimal control strategy, the values in pitch angle and velocity show a general increase in magnitude with H_s and T_p . Overall, the pattern and values in pitch angle and velocity remain similar to the results observed when using a passive strategy (see Section 5.3.1.1).

Regarding the PTO force, both the peak and RMS values present some significant difference compared to the values observed when using a passive strategy: the peak values are about 10 times larger (with peaks of up to 8MN), whilst the RMS PTO force increases to up to 1.6MN (vs. 0.2MN when considering a passive strategy). Moreover, the largest RMS values of PTO force are observed at smaller H_s that in the case of a passive strategy.

5.3.1.3 Variation c1: Spread waves

In variation c1, the input waves considered have directional spreading and an angle of incidence of 0° and cover the Peniche scatter diagram. The control strategy considered is sub-optimal.

Figure 5.8 shows the peak and RMS values for the pitch angle, PTO force and pitch velocity.

Figure 5.8 Matrices of peak (left column) and RMS (right column) of pitch angle (in degrees, top row), PTO force (for PTO1, in MN, middle row) and pitch velocity (in rad/s, bottom row) – variation c1

Overall, the spreading of the incident energy over multiple directions leads to a general decrease in the metrics observed. In particular, the RMS values in pitch angle, velocity and PTO force, a decrease of about 10-15% can be seen between the case in unidirectional waves and the directional spread wave case.

Regarding the peak velocities, the values remain fairly similar between the unidirectional and directional spread wave cases for the different sea states considered, with an average ratio of 1. The variation in range of peak velocities in the colour maps between the unidirectional (Figure 5.7) and directional spread (Figure 5.8) wave cases is due to a single high peak of 7rad/s in unidirectional wave at sea state H_s 4.25m and T_p 12.5s .

Finally, the impact of spreading on peak PTO force and peak pitch angle is less significant (decrease by less than 3%).

5.3.1.4 Variation c2: Oblique waves

In variation c2, the input waves considered are unidirectional, with an angle of incidence varying between 0° and 15°. The sea state is characterised by a significant wave height of 2.25m and a peak period of 12.5s, corresponding to the most energetic sea state at the Peniche site. The control strategy considered is sub-optimal.

Figure 5.9 shows the peak and RMS values of pitch angle, PTO force and pitch velocity.

Figure 5.9 Distribution with incoming wave direction – peak (left column) and RMS (right column) of pitch angle (in degrees, top row), PTO force (for PTO1, in MN, middle row) and pitch velocity (in rad/s, bottom row) – variation c2

As expected, increasing the angle of incidence tends to reduce the range of motion (angle and velocity in pitch) experienced by the flap, along with the PTO force (RMS and peaks). Overall, the decrease observed reaches about 3% for the different metrics considered when increasing the angle of incidence from 0° to 15°. Given the symmetry of the problem, it can be assumed that a similar decrease would be observed when decreasing the angle of incidence from 0° to -15°.

5.3.1.5 ULS characteristic values

To obtain ULS estimates, a Gumbel distribution was fitted to the peaks in the time series of the PTO force for the energetic sea state (i.e. $H_s = 2.25\text{m}$, $T_p = 12.5\text{s}$) and for variations a, b and c1. The 10-, 50- and 100-year return period characteristic values of PTO loads (i.e. the 90th, 98th and 99th quantiles of the probability distribution) are presented in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4 Characteristic ULS PTO force (MN): 10-, 50- and 100-year return period – DLC 1.1

Return period	10-year	50-year	100-year
Variation a	0.9	1.1	1.2
Variation b	4.9	5.7	6.1
Variation c1	4.1	4.8	5.1

Overall, the ULS PTO force characteristic values when considering the proposed sub-optimal control strategy are approximately 4 to 6 times larger than those observed when using a passive strategy. When comparing the ULS PTO forces in unidirectional and spread waves, it can be seen that the distribution of the incident wave energy over a range of directions leads to characteristic values about 15% lower than in the unidirectional case.

5.3.2 DLC 1.4 Power Production

In DLC 1.4, two water depths were considered, corresponding to the 50-year return water levels presented in Table 4.2. The environmental conditions are represented using a *FWG* defined based on the 1-year return period with the highest significant wave height (H_s, T_p) = (5.88m, 14.4s). The investigations included the considerations of slap and slam forces – and results in terms of peak forces (including PTO forces) are presented in the following sub-sections for each water depth considered. Further refinements on the wave input may be considered at a later stage, e.g. using outputs from the numerical wave model developed under Task 1.1, where nearshore wave conditions should be more accurately defined.

5.3.2.1 Maximum water level

Figure 5.10 presents the peak values for the PTO forces (PTO1 and PTO2, both using the same damping coefficient throughout the simulation) and the slap and slam forces (in surge and heave, respectively), for the different wave seeds considered. The mean of the peak values from each wave seeds are presented in Table 5.5.

Figure 5.10 Variation of peak force with wave seed: PTO force (top), slam force in heave (bottom left) and slap force in surge (bottom right) – DLC 1.4, water depth 14m

Table 5.5 Mean peak force values: PTO force, slam force in heave and slap force in surge – DLC 1.4, water depth 14m

	PTO force	Slam force (heave)	Slap force (surge)
Mean peak value (MN)	23.03	57.92	239.57

Overall, the slap force appears to be the most dominant force, with a mean peak value (c. 240MN) in average more than 4 times higher than the slam force in heave (c. 60MN) and up to 10 times the PTO force (c. 23MN). The magnitude of the loads reported in Table 5.5 highlights the potential limits of the rigid body formulation, warranting further investigation (outside the scope of MegaRoller). The use of a non-rigid body formulation may introduce some additional fidelity in the overall response estimates, as the structural integrity of the prime mover (i.e. the flap) may be compromised under such load envelope, potentially reducing the PTO loading at the expense of the prime mover’s integrity.

5.3.2.2 Minimum water level

In the minimum water level variation, the same *FWG* was considered in the context of the 50-year return low water level (water depth of 10m). As mentioned in Section 4.5.1, it is noted that, although the DLC uses a sea state on the 1-year environmental contour, the *FWG* wave height (11.17m) appears very high with regard to the low water level – modifications to the guidance issued in [WES, 2016] may be required to address such extreme situations. As in the maximum water level case, further refinements on the wave input may be considered at a later stage, e.g. using outputs from the numerical wave model developed under Task 1.1, where nearshore wave conditions should be more accurately defined.

In a first step, the DLC was run using the same machine state as in the maximum water level variation (see Section 5.3.2.1). The results show that the range of motion and forces estimated becomes extremely large – see Figure 5.11. In particular, the slam and slap forces spike during events where the flap pitches back to a vertical position from a trough while the next crest of a wave is incoming.

Figure 5.11 Time series of slam force in heave (top left), slap force in surge (top right) and pitch angle (bottom) – 0s is the instant of arrival of the focus wave group peak – the vertical axis for the slam and slap forces was cropped at 50MN

Due to the unfeasibly high forces observed, a situation where the flap motion was further restrained by the end stop, with an angular range of motion limited to 16° before the end stop starts acting, was considered. Figure 5.12 presents an example of the time-series of slap and slam forces (in surge and heave, respectively), along with the corresponding pitch angle of the flap.

Figure 5.12 Time series of slam force in heave (top left), slap force in surge (top right) and pitch angle (bottom) – 0s is the instant of arrival of the focus wave group peak – restrained range of motion – the vertical axis for the slam and slap forces was cropped at 50MN

Using the restrained end stop, the peak values for the PTO, slap and slam forces (in surge and heave, respectively) were estimated for the different wave seeds considered, as shown in Figure 5.13. The mean peak values are presented in Table 5.6.

Similar to the higher water depth case (see Section 5.3.2.1), the slap force appears to be the most dominant force, with a peak value (c. 240MN) in average more than 4 times larger than the slam force in heave (c. 53MN) and about 10 times the PTO force (c. 26MN).

Figure 5.13 Variation of peak force with wave seed: PTO force (top), slam force in heave (bottom left) and slap force in surge (bottom right) – LC 1.4, water depth 10m

Table 5.6 Mean peak force values: PTO force, slam force in heave and slap force in surge – DLC 1.4, water depth 10m

	PTO force	Slam force (heave)	Slap force (surge)
Mean peak value (MN)	26.21	53.69	236.98

5.3.3 DLC 2.1 Power Production Plus Occurrence of Fault

In DLC 2.1, a fault in the control system was considered. The fault consisted of a high damping value for PTO2, applied throughout the simulation. Figure 5.14 presents the peak PTO forces estimated for the different wave seeds considered. The corresponding mean peak values (for PTO1 and PTO2), are presented in Table 5.7.

Figure 5.14 Variation of peak PTO force with wave seed

Table 5.7 Mean peak PTO forces for PTO1 (power production) and PTO2 (with fault)

	PTO1	PTO2
Mean peak value (MN)	6.51	34.40

Similar to the analysis conducted for DLC 1.4 (see Section 5.3.2), a Gumbel distribution was fitted to the peaks in PTO force extracted from each seed considered to derive the characteristic loads for the PTOs. The 10-, 50- and 100-year return period characteristic values of PTO loads (i.e. the 90th, 98th and 99th quantiles of the probability distribution) are presented in Table 5.5.

Table 5.8 Characteristic ULS PTO force (PTO1, power production and PTO2, with fault): 10-, 50- and 100-year return period – DLC 2.1

Return period	10-year	50-year	100-year
PTO1 force (MN)	11.54	12.51	12.87
PTO2 force (MN)	60.98	66.07	67.97

Overall, the PTO loading appears to be significantly asymmetrical, with a ULS characteristic value for the PTO load of more than 5 times larger for the PTO with fault than with the PTO operating normally. It should be noted that the PTO forces, and therefore the characteristic values, presented in this subsection are highly dependent on the assumed PTO settings, in particular the damping coefficient and assumed fault scenario. As the project progresses, the assumptions could be revisited, and the loads recalculated.

5.3.4 DLC 7.1 Parked Plus Occurrence of Fault

DLC 7.1 considered a ‘parked with fault’ scenario, where one of the PTO units was assumed to be disconnected (i.e., applying zero damping) and the other was assumed to be ‘jammed’, therefore applying a high damping coefficient. The damping coefficient for the ‘jammed’ PTO was set to 2x the highest coefficient selected by the ‘sub-optimal’ control strategy (see Section 3.4). This estimate could be refined as the project progresses and the fault scenario modelled in more detail (see Section 6).

The assessment of DLC 7.1 was conducted in three main stages, described as following:

- Initial screening over the 11 sea states samples from the 1-year return environmental contour.
- Detailed load analysis for the sea state leading to the highest PTO loads.
- Structural analysis, using the structural dynamics model.

The results of each step are presented in the following sections.

5.3.4.1 Initial screening

Firstly, the 11 combinations of H_s and T_p listed in Table 4.9 were analysed using a simplified model, with the aim of identifying which sea state leads to the highest loads. For this initial analysis the additions to the WEC-Sim model described in Section 3.3 to Section 3.8, such as the slap and slam correction, hydrodynamic database and the structural dynamics module, were not included and the simulations were run for a shorter time of 30 minutes to enable faster comparisons of the different sea states. Table 5.9 displays a summary of the key metrics extracted for each sea state.

Table 5.9 Comparison of key metrics across 11 extreme sea states

Sea state			Surge excitation force [MN]		Flap pitch angle [deg]		PTO force [MN]	
ID	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	RMS	Peak	RMS	Peak	RMS	Peak
1	1.61	5.54	1.41	5.18	1.9	6.7	1.40	5.02
2	2.29	6.64	2.43	8.31	3.7	13.5	2.27	7.79
3	2.94	7.75	3.39	10.72	6.1	21.5	3.24	10.39
4	3.56	8.86	4.14	13.01	9.2	31.2	4.28	12.81
5	4.16	9.96	4.64	15.47	12.8	48.7	5.27	16.58
6	4.73	11.1	5.01	17.58	17.5	67.7	6.31	19.58
7	5.24	12.2	5.25	17.24	22.2	81.6	7.15	22.61
8	5.64	13.3	5.34	17.73	26.6	88.5	7.81	24.35
9	5.88	14.4	5.31	17.40	30.0	90.0	8.18	25.50
10	5.81	15.5	4.90	16.48	30.5	90.0	7.85	24.53
11	5.10	16.6	4.05	14.10	28.0	83.6	6.95	21.78

In general, higher H_s values are seen to result in higher PTO loads as expected. Sea state 9 ($H_s = 5.88\text{m}$, $T_p = 14.4\text{s}$) can be seen to result in the both the highest peak PTO force and the highest RMS value and was therefore selected for the detailed load analysis.

5.3.4.2 Detailed load analysis

As a second step, sea state 9 was then analysed using the standard WEC-Sim model, which includes the slap and slam and hydrodynamic database add-ons. Three separate 1-hour simulations were run using different input wave seeds, in order to model a 3-hour storm. Figure 5.15 shows an example of the resulting PTO force time history. The extreme negative peaks in PTO force correspond to instances where the end stop is active (see Section 3.2), as shown in Figure 5.16. Peaks greater than 40MN, calculated based on absolute values, were therefore assumed to be fictitious, appearing only as a result of numerical instability in the model, and were therefore excluded when post-processing the results.

Results were used to derive RMS values, an average of the peaks extracted from each seed and characteristic loads for the ‘jammed’ PTO, which are listed in Table 5.10. To derive the characteristic values of the PTO load, a Gumbel distribution was fitted to the peaks in PTO force extracted from all 3 simulations. This distribution was then used to extract loads for three sample return probabilities; 90%, 98% and 99%, which can in turn be used to derive loads with different return periods. For example, for a distribution fitted to the peaks from a 1-year extreme sea state (i.e., this example), the 98th percentile value corresponds to a 1-in-50-year return period. Figure 5.18 shows the peaks used and resulting characteristic values.

Figure 5.19 shows the probability density function used to derive the characteristic values.

It should be noted that the PTO force and therefore the characteristic values presented in this section are highly dependent on the assumed PTO settings, in particular the damping coefficient and assumed fault scenario. As the project progresses, the assumptions may be re-visited, and the loads re-calculated.

Although this assessment focused on the PTO units, the coupled assessments in WEC-Sim also highlighted the effect of the proposed control strategy on the motion of the flap. By disconnecting the PTO in a ‘parked’ scenario, the damping force acting on the flap is reduced. Even after the addition of an end stop to limit the flap pitch motion, extreme sea states lead to large flap pitch motions approaching 90° as illustrated in Figure 5.17. In extreme cases, prioritising survival of the PTO unit in this manner could result in substantially higher loads on the flap.

Figure 5.15 PTO force for an example 10-minute time-history

Figure 5.16 PTO force and end stop pitching moment example time history

Figure 5.17 Flap pitch and angle and wave elevation example time history

Table 5.10 DLC 7.1 PTO force metrics

	PTO force metrics [MN]				
	RMS	Mean peak value	Characteristic load		
			10-year	50-year	100-year
Seed 1	7.25	9.44	46.97	55.19	58.71
Seed 2	7.53				
Seed 3	8.02				

Figure 5.18 Peaks in absolute PTO force extracted from each simulation and the calculated extreme values

Figure 5.19 Probability density function for PTO force

5.3.4.3 Structural analysis

The fault scenario considered leads to unequal loads on the two PTO units and therefore has the potential to bend the flap. As a final step, the same sea state was therefore analysed using the structural dynamics model, enabling coupled hydro-elastic analysis. To further investigate the effect of material stiffness on the behaviour of the MegaRoller WEC, a short case study was conducted using three different assumed stiffnesses. The ‘baseline’ case represents a steel flap. Two other cases were then compared; one using a ‘rigid’ material (Young’s Modulus increased by a factor of 100) and a second using a more flexible material where the Young’s Modulus was reduced by a factor of 4 when compared to the baseline case. This could, for example, represent a more flexible composite material.

Due to the increased computational requirements associated with running the structural dynamics model, each model was only run for a 5-minute simulation as opposed to the 1-hour simulation used previously. Comparisons were therefore limited to the use of RMS values as more peaks would be required to generate statistically significant characteristic loads.

Figure 5.20 compares the PTO force for an example 100s transient. Results for the baseline case are seen to match closely to the ‘rigid’ material. This suggests that, for this example, bending of the flap is not sufficient to influence the PTO loads. This result is reflected in the similar RMS values presented in Table 5.11.

However, larger differences are seen when comparing the ‘flexible’ material. The lower stiffness leads to larger local deformations, as illustrated in Figure 5.21, which shows the out-of-plane (global Y direction) deformation at the time corresponding to a local maximum in PTO force. At the PTO interface, these deformations change the local velocity which in turn influences the PTO force at the next iteration. As illustrated in Figure 5.20, this can create increasingly unstable response and higher PTO loads, as shown by the increase in the RMS value for the flexible case.

During trial simulations of a longer duration this hydro-elastic coupling was seen to cause resonance and instability in the model when used with flexible materials. This highlights the potential importance of structural dynamics, but presents difficulties in obtaining a stable solution for longer simulations. Future development could seek to increase the stability and computational efficiency of the structural dynamics module in order to make it more applicable for a wider range of load cases (see Section 6). In particular, modifications could be investigated with the aim of stabilising the prediction of the motion of the flap’s centre of gravity, which in turn stabilises the loads predictions in WEC-Sim.

Figure 5.20 Comparison of PTO Force for three different material stiffnesses

Table 5.11 RMS PTO Force for each material stiffness

	RMS PTO force [MN]
Rigid	9.38
Steel	9.42
Flexible	11.43

Figure 5.21 Out of Plane deflection (UY) at an example peak in PTO force (t=226s)

6 CONCLUSIONS

6.1 Key Findings

In this report, the initial, priority load calculation effort that will inform the primary design of the MegaRoller WEC, and in particular the PTO, were presented. Details were provided regarding the methodologies, assumptions, models and initial results, in alignment with the DLC prioritisation.

The priority load assessment was numerically based using a formulation that simultaneously account for all relevant load sources. For the priority DLCs, a fully coupled point and distributed load model based on WEC-Sim was used to assess the loads. For DLC 7.1, the load model was coupled to a finite element model for structural modelling, enabling an initial assessment of the impact of the distributed loading contributions over the flap on the PTO.

At a high-level, and when considering the complete WEC system, the results identify some of the potential limits of the rigid body formulation in face of the estimated load envelope. For example, in DLC 1.4 slap and slam forces were found to reach values substantially higher than the PTO loads observed, which may indicate that the structural integrity of the prime mover is compromised for such events. Moreover, the results showed that a revision of the modes of operations may be required, in particular to limit the range of motion of the flap or forces experienced in some cases of low tides. Although the MegaRoller project focuses on the development of the PTO system, the findings stress the importance of coupled assessments to identify critical interdependencies between subsystems, which may in turn relate to key design aspects such as balancing the survival of the PTO vs. survival of the WEC.

Finally, it was found that DLCs considering a fault e.g. in the control system (i.e. DLC 2.1 and DLC 7.1) are likely to be critical to the PTO design, with PTO loads on the faulty PTO (PTO2) more than five times larger than the functional PTO (PTO1). An initial investigation into the effects of structural flexibility showed the assumed steel flap to be relatively stiff and, for the example cases studied, local deformations had minimal effect on the PTO loads. However, the use of more flexible materials was seen to have a more significant impact, with PTO loads increasing. Model stability also suffered with the introduction of structural flexibility, highlighting some of the computational challenges involved.

It should be noted that the different metrics, and the associated characteristic values where relevant, presented in Section 5 are highly dependent on the assumed PTO settings, in particular the damping coefficient and assumed fault scenario. As the project progresses, the assumptions could be revisited, and the loads recalculated (see Section 6.2).

6.2 Next Steps

Following the completion of the initial load calculations, the immediate next steps in the MegaRoller project include:

- As an immediate next step, the loading envelope that the drive train faces will be passed on as an input to the mechanical design tasks of the new test bench (Task 1.5) and of the MegaRoller PTO (Task 2.3). The estimated loads will inform the design effort in terms of e.g. materials and assembly options between the MegaRoller drive train, flap and foundation.
- Following the integration of the PTO on the test rig, a measurement campaign will be initiated that will feed a validation exercise for the numerical models developed. The key objective is to assess the level of fidelity of the WEC response and loading estimates.

Regarding the numerical load model developed, future work (potentially outside the scope of the MegaRoller project) may address the following aspects:

- Additional variations under DLC 1.1 may be investigated, considering more complex PTO settings and control strategies, in particular informed by WP2.
- In further ULS investigations, a full environmental approach may be used, where a large number of samples is taken within the 100-year contour, leading to reliability (of 'survival') functions.
- The goodness of fit of the distribution used to estimate the ULS characteristic loads could be monitored, to ensure that the underlying physical processes are well represented by the selected distribution.
- The impact of the lever arm length on WEC performance could be assessed.
- Further complexity could be introduced to the drag formulation via e.g. the use of non-constant C_d estimates.
- The initial assumptions on the key structural properties used in the FE model could be revised as the design progresses.
- The structural dynamics module could be further developed to increase stability, enabling it to be applied to a wider range of load cases and longer simulations.
- A stronger coupling between the load and FE models could be envisaged, e.g. by updating the hydrodynamic coefficients in the load model based on the deformations estimated in the FE model at each time step. This could be done e.g. by extending the database of hydrodynamic coefficients to include different deformed shapes.
- The structural dynamics add-on to WEC-Sim could be used to analyse more load cases (e.g. DLC 1.1).
- Modelling of the PTO could be updated as the design progresses. For example, more detailed modelling of potential fault scenarios and dominant load cases could be considered based on updated design parameters, such as target damping coefficients and the control strategy.

Finally, potential future work could also investigate DLCs focusing on other subsystems and / or prime mover structural design.

7 REFERENCES

- [D1.1, 2018] D1.1 *Advanced Wave-Structure Interaction Model – Theory and User Manual*
Deliverable Leader: CAT
Dated 24/10/2018
- [D2.3, 2018] D2.3 *Conceptual Control System Design*
Deliverable Leader: AWE
Dated 29/10/2018
- [D6.6, 2019] D6.6 Standard Gap Analysis
Deliverable Leader: CAT
Due date for submission: 31/04/2019
- [DNV GL, 2007] GL Rules and Guidelines IV-6-4 (2007)
Offshore Technology - Structural Design.
- [DNV GL, 2017] DNVGL Recommended practice (2017)
DNVGL-RP-C205 Environmental Conditions and Environmental Loads
Edition August 2017
- [DNV, 2005] *DNV Guidelines on Design and Operation of Wave Energy Converters*
May 2005
The Carbon Trust
- [DNV, 2008] Det Norske Veritas AS (DNV)
DNV-OSS-312 Certification of Tidal and Wave Energy Converters
October 2008
- [Eckert-Gallup et al., 2016] A. C. Eckert-Gallup et al. (2016)
Application of principal component analysis (PCA) and improved joint probability distributions to the inverse first-order reliability method (I-FORM) for predicting extreme sea states.
Ocean Engineering, Vol. 112, pp. 307 – 319
- [EDF, 2019] Electricité de France (EDF)
Finite Element Analysis of Structures and Thermo-mechanics for Studies and Research
1989 – 2019
Online: www.code-aster.org, last opened 12/04/2019
- [EMEC, 2009] The European Marine Energy Centre (EMEC)
Guidelines for Design Basis of Marine Energy Conversion Systems
2009
- [GA, 2018] Grant Agreement number: 763959 — MegaRoller — H2020-LCE-2016-2017/H2020-LCE-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage
Dated 26/03/2018
- [IEC, 2016] IEC TS 62600-2:2016
Technical Specifications TS 114 – Marine Energy – Wave, Tidal and other water current converters
Part 2: Design requirements for marine energy systems
Dated 10/08/2016
- [Scriven, 2019] Scriven J., Laporte Weywada P., Cruz J. (2019)
Introducing non-rigid body structural dynamics to WEC-Sim
Submitted to EWTEC for publication at EWTEC 2019.

- [SDWED, 2014] Hameddni B., Bittencourt Ferreira C. (2014)
Deliverable D5.2 Generic WEC risk ranking and failure mode analysis
Dated 18/05/2014
- [WES, 2016] Wave Energy Scotland (2016).
Structural Forces and Stresses for Wave Energy Devices – Landscaping Study.
Report prepared by Ove Arup & Partners (Scotland) Ltd and Cruz Atcheson
Consulting Engineers Lda.